

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL FOOT GEL FOR CRACKS USING FLAX SEEDS

¹Kuljeet Kaur, ²Devid Rana, ³Neeraj Kumar, ⁴Dr Hina Chadha

^{1,4} Department of Pharmacy, Vishveshwarya Group of Institutions,

^{2,3} Vishveshwarya College of Pharmacy,

Dadri, G. Noida, Gautam Budh Nagar, India

Abstract : Cracked heels, a common foot condition characterized by dry, thickened skin and painful fissures, are particularly prevalent in rural areas. Contributing factors include the lack of oil glands on the soles, improper footwear, poor hygiene, and prolonged exposure to harsh environmental conditions. This condition often leads to infections caused by bacteria and fungi, further aggravating discomfort and foot odor. The primary causes of cracked heels include aging, pressure, skin deficiencies, obesity, and neglect of proper foot care.

To address this issue, a herbal foot crack gel was developed using flax seeds (both oil and mucilage), aloe gel, and glycerine as active ingredients. The gel was formulated to moisturize, soothe, and promote healing of cracked heels. Three formulations were evaluated based on various parameters, such as pH, spreadability, stability and microbial contamination, etc. The results indicated that all three formulations exhibited a pH range of 7-8 and were easily washable. Formulations F2 and F3 showed better spreadability and stability compared to F1, maintaining their quality for up to three months. No microbial growth was observed in any of the formulations.

The herbal foot crack gel demonstrated effective soothing and healing properties, with stable performance over time. This formulation offers a promising alternative to synthetic treatments, providing a safe and natural solution for cracked heels, particularly in underserved rural populations.

Index Terms - Footcare, crack heels, flax seeds, aloe vera, herbal formulation

I. INTRODUCTION

The feet, an essential part of the human body, are constantly exposed to friction and the external environment. Because the soles lack oil glands, the skin on the feet becomes prone to dryness, which, if neglected, can lead to cracked heels (also known as fissures). This issue is particularly common in rural areas, especially in Indian villages, where around 80% of the population resides. Many people in these areas work in farms with wet soil and water, often neglecting proper foot care, which contributes to the development of cracked heels.¹

Crack Heels-Symptoms & Causes¹⁻³

Cracked heels are characterized by thickened, often yellow or brown calluses around the edges of the heel, accompanied by excessively dry skin. In rural areas, as well as in slums or some urban neighborhoods, improper footwear is a common issue, leading to infections when dirt, fungi, and bacteria enter through the cracks and wounds in the heels. *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, bacterium, is known to cause foot odor due to bacterial decomposition. Additionally, other infections can arise from microorganisms like *Candida albicans*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*, which thrive in unhygienic, cracked feet. These infections can cause significant discomfort and even pain for those affected.

Figure 1: Appearance of cracked heels³

The most common causes of cracked heels are reported to be:

- **Absence of oil glands:** Skin around the heels has a relatively small number or almost no oil glands. Thus, tissues present here are less elastic, and if skin is dried and not moisturized from outside, it leads to cracks.
- **Deficiencies:** Lack of vitamins, minerals & zinc in your diet can adversely affect your heel health.
- **Pressure:** Spending a long time standing at work or home can stress the skin on heels.
- **Ageing skin:** Thick, dry, scaly skin loses its elasticity with age and as person gets older, the incidence of cracks becomes higher.
- **Other foot disorders:** Athlete's foot, psoriasis, eczema, thyroid disease, diabetes and some other skin condition can also lead to cracked heels.
- **Obesity:** Being overweight can increase pressure on the fat pad under the heel. This can cause it to expand sideways and thus cracks may appear.
- **Neglecting hygiene:** Unclean feet, if left neglected for long, can further aggravate cracked heels. Also, external penetration of dirt, bacteria through cuts and wounds may give rise to infections.
- **Improper footwear:** Open footwear exposes heels to environmental conditions and loss of moisture leading to dry skin. If neglected for long with improper care, may lead to cracks.
- **Excessive walking:** Wearing improper shoes, open sandals, barefoot walking for more than 3-4 hours daily may also lead to cracked heels.
- **Hot and dry weather:** Weather plays an important role for a healthy skin. Hot and dry conditions may further dry the skin if not taken care of.

FLAX- A NATURAL INGREDIENT FOR CRACKED HEEL⁴⁻¹⁰

Flax– An overview

Flax (Botanical name: *Linum usitatissimum*, Family-Linaceae) is fibrous crop of dicotyledonous annual plant, that grows to a height of 12–40 in (30–100 cm). It has a distinct main stem and a short taproot, It's root branches are thin and can extend to a depth of 3–4 ft (90–120 cm) in light soil. The fruit of flax is a five-celled capsule, which contains 10 seeds, when filled (Figure 2). The plant is grown in many parts of the world, mainly in temperate regions. It is inhabitant to West Asia and the Mediterranean coastal lands, Asia (minor part), Egypt, Algeria, Tunis, Spain, Italy, and Greece. In all these areas, only flax (fiber) is cultivated, whereas in south-west Asia, including Turkestan, Afghanistan and India, only oil types of flax are grown. Because of its attractive flowers, flax is also grown as an ornamental plant in gardens. Flax has been used both -- as fiber and for the seed.

Figure 2: Flax fruit (five celled capsule)⁵

The flax is taxonomically classified as:

Kingdom: Plantae
 Division: Magnoliophyta
 Class: Magnoliopsida
 Order: Malpighiales
 Family: Linaceae
 Genus: *Linum*
 Species: *usitatissimum*

Common names of flax are: Flaxseed (English), Linseed (Common), Tisi (Hindi), Alasi (Sanskrit)

The Latin name of flax means 'very useful', as each part of flax plant is utilized commercially (either directly or after processing).

a). Flax seeds

Flax seeds have many nutritional characteristics, as they contain 20–25% protein and 40–45% fatty acids. While, the cotyledon in the seed contains 76% of the protein and 75% of the lipids, only 23% of the lipids and 16% of the protein are found in the endosperm. Flaxseed's lipid makes it a good source of Omega 3 fatty acids, particularly, alpha linolenic acid, which can be up to 52% of total fatty acids. Flaxseed is also a good source of phenolic compounds known as lignans, a colloid gum (mucilage), vitamins (A, C, F and E) and mineral (P, Mg, K, Na, Fe, Cu, Mn and Zn).

Flax seeds also contain soluble and insoluble dietary fibers in a ratio that varies between 20: 80 and 40:60. The major insoluble fiber fraction consists of cellulose and lignin and the soluble fiber fractions are the mucilage gums.

Flaxseeds are available in two basic varieties: (1) brown (2) yellow or golden (Figure 3). Brown flax is better known and used as an ingredient in paints, varnish, fiber and cattle feed, however both the varieties are used for their nutritional properties.

Figure 3: Varieties of flax seeds⁵

b). Flax seed oil

Composition: The oil in flaxseed is mostly stored in cotyledons. It contains 98% of triacylglycerols, 0.9% phospholipids and 0.1% free fatty acids (FA). It has low saturated fatty acid content (9%), moderate monounsaturated fatty acid content (18%), and high polyunsaturated fatty acid content (73%). The primary fatty acid in flaxseed oil is - linolenic acid (LA), which ranges from 39.00 to 60.42%, followed by oleic, linoleic, palmitic and stearic acids, which offer an excellent Omega-6: Omega-3 fatty acid ratio of roughly 3:1. Flaxseed oil is naturally high in anti-oxidant like tocopherols and beta-carotene. It also contains alpha linolenic acid (ALA), and gamma linolenic acid (GLA). Usually, dry and sensitive skin is treated with topical applications of oils containing n-6 FA, LA, or GLA.

Use of flaxseeds oil in cosmetics and skincare: Due to the presence of omega-3-fatty acids in flax seeds oil, it has been medicinally used in several inflammatory conditions of the skin such as acne, psoriasis, rosacea and eczema. It can help overcoming dry skin, and even the pain caused due to sunburns, and thus reduces red skin irritation. Due to its anti-oxidant properties, flax oil provides hair and skin care benefits. It rejuvenates the skin and softens the appearance of fine lines and wrinkles. Essential fatty acids increase moisture to keep skin soft and hydrated.

c). Flax seed mucilage

Mucilage is present in the seeds and soft stems of several plants. The flaxseed coat and endosperm is made up of 6 layers, and mucilage comes from the secondary wall material in the outermost layer. It is easily extracted from the seed coat by soaking in water. When hydrated, the mucilage cells swell, and their content exude on the surface of the seeds. Mucilage makes up approximately 8% of the total seed weight.

Chemical Composition: Flax seed mucilage contains between 50–80% carbohydrates and 20% and 4% of proteins and ash. The major constituent of flax mucilage consists of two polysaccharide components, neutral and acidic. The neutral fraction contains L-arabinose, D-xylose and D-galactose in a mole ratio of 3:5:6.2:1 and the acidic fraction contains L-rhamnose, L-fucose, L-galactose, and D galacturonic acid in a mole ratio of 2.6:1:1.4:1.7.

Uses in cosmetic preparations: Flax seed mucilage has emulsifying and foaming properties, viscosity, gelation and water binding capacity. Flax mucilage also exhibits surface activity and the ability to stabilize oil/water emulsions and foams. It has been used in emulsion preparation in order to enhance stability. It stabilizes the emulsions by increasing the viscosity and decreasing the interfacial tension. The properties of this plant extracts support is used as a part of ingredient in cosmetic formulation. Apart from that, it has biologically active role in the prevention and/or treatment of certain diseases too.

ALOE VERA¹¹⁻¹⁴

Aloe vera, (Family: Liliaceae), is a stemless or very short-stemmed perennial succulent or xerophytes (Figure 4a) with elongated and peaked leaves in which large amounts of water are stored in the tissue. It is locally known as 'Guarpatha'. The plant is the source of two commonly used products that differ in their chemical composition as well as therapeutic abilities:

- ❑ **Gel** : The inner leaf pulp is composed of large thin-walled parenchymal cells containing *Aloe vera* gel (a synonym to inner leaf, inner leaf fillet, or fillet). The gel or juice is clear viscous material and makes up the majority of the plant by volume (Figure 4b). It is separated from the parenchymal tissues in the leaves of plant and is used in cosmetic preparations.
- ❑ **Yellow sap**: yellow sap or latex, present in the pericyclic tubule cell, is bitter and an active cathartic pharmaceutical product known simply as the Aloe.

Figure 4: a) Aloe plant;¹³ b) Gel present in aloe leaves.¹⁴

Composition and uses of Aloe vera gel:

Overall Aloe vera leaves contains more than 75 potentially active constituents that are mainly present in the aloe gel and the yellow sap of the plant, such as vitamins, enzymes, minerals, sugars, lignin, saponins, salicylic acids and amino acids. Sugars present in Aloe provide monosaccharides (glucose and fructose) and polysaccharides: (glucomannans/polymannose). These are derived from the mucilage layer of the plant and are known as mucopolysaccharides. Polysaccharide in the gel helps in binding moisture into the skin. Aloe stimulates fibroblasts which produce collagen and elastin fibre making the skin more elastic and less wrinkled. It also has cohesive effect on the superficial flaking epidermal cells by sticking them together, which softens the cells by sticking them together. The amino acid present in it also softens harden skin cell.

Other compounds present in Aloe vera has wound and burn healing properties, antifungal, antiviral, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and immuno-modulatory effects. It can be applied topically as an emollient for burns, sunburn and mild abrasion and for inflammatory skin disorder, and thus is used for centuries for its health, beauty, medicinal and skin care properties.

II. MATERIALS & METHODOLOGY

Collection of materials & ingredients used: All the materials mentioned in Table 1 were collected from local market and chemical stores.

Preparation of flax seed sample: Flax seeds were procured from an authentic source & were cleaned with distilled water. They were dried in shade for 72 hours (at 25⁰C), and then stored in air tight storage container for further work at room temperature.

Extraction of flax seed oil: Mechanical grinding/Cold Pressure method

Oil was extracted from the flax seeds by first roasting it at 105⁰ for a few minutes, and then applying physical pressure, and finally filtering the oil. The oil obtained was yellow in color. It was kept in amber colored bottle, and sealed properly.

Extraction of flax seed mucilage: By Heating Method

Ten grams of the brown flaxseed grains were boiled in 300 ml of distilled water for 60 min at 80-90⁰c on a magnetic stirrer at a speed of 500 rpm. The seeds were then separated from the colloidal solution by filtration through Nylon cloth. In order to preserve the filter sample for future research, 1% sodium benzoate was added to it and kept it in an airtight container.

Preparation of aloe vera extract:

Fresh and healthy aloe vera leaf was collected and the latex was drained out by keeping it vertically for a few minutes. When latex stopped oozing, the leaf was washed properly with distilled water and cleaned with dried muslin cloth. After completely drying, the outer part of the leaf was removed longitudinally using a sterile knife. The pulp/gel obtained was further crushed in a mixer grinder, and strained using a muslin cloth to remove any attached fibres. The aloe juice (i.e the obtained filtrate) was heated at 50-60⁰C for a few minutes by continuously stirring to avoid charring. When water content was reduced, the obtained extract was stored at cool place (temperature upto 10⁰C).

Preparation of foot care gel:

Step 1: Water phase (water soluble ingredients/flax seed mucilage) and oil phase (oil soluble ingredients/flax oil) were heated separately up to 75-80⁰C. After heating, the aqueous phase was added to the oil phase (as per the quantities mentioned in the Table 1) while being continuously stirred to prepare the 3 formulations.

Step 2: This w/o emulsion, was then mixed with the aloe extract (which acts as gel base) in a pestle and mortar to obtain three formulations namely F1, F2 and F3 (of 50 ml each). The homogenized texture, is then cooled down to 30-35 ⁰C and preservatives and rose oil essence were added. Finally, the gel was stored in air tight container for the study of stability test and other physiochemical parameters.

Ingredients	Quantity		
	F1	F2	F3
Flax seed oil	20 ml	25 ml	30 ml
Flax seed mucilage	15 ml	10 ml	5 ml
Aloe Vera gel	10 ml	10 ml	10 ml
Glycerin	4.5 ml	4.5 ml	4.5 ml
Sodium Benzoate (1%)	0.5 ml	0.5 ml	0.5 ml
Rose oil	q.s	q.s	q.s
Total volume	50 ml	50 ml	50 ml

Table 1: Formulation of herbal foot gel for cracked heels

Parameters for evaluation of herbal foot crack gel:

- Appearance:** The appearance of the gel was determined by its colour, texture and odour.
- pH:** One gm of the sample was weighed and dissolved in 100ml of distilled water at room temperature. Its pH was determined through pH paper.
- Spreadability:** Spread ability may be expressed by the extent of the area to which the topical application spreads when applied to the affected parts on the skin.
- Washability:** This test was carried out by applying the little amount of gel over the skin and was then washed under the water.
- Homogeneity:** The formulations were tested for the homogeneity by visual appearance and touch.
- Irritancy test:** A patch of gel was applied in an area (1 sq.cm) on the left hand dorsal surface and the time was noted. Irritancy, erythema, edema was checked, if any for regular intervals, upto 24 hours and reported.
- Test for stability:** The formulated gel was transferred into a suitable glass container and sealed well. The glass bottle was placed at normal environmental conditions for 3 months. The glass bottle was opened after every one month and checked for any physical instability such as changes in color, odor and consistency of the formulation or any signs of bacterial or fungal growths.

III. OBSERVATION & RESULTS

The herbal foot crack gel was prepared using flax seeds as main ingredient, along with aloe gel and glycerine. Various evaluation parameters were performed for the effectiveness and stability of the gel (and given in Table 2).

- All the 3 formulations were found to be in the range of 7-8 pH (Figure 5), and all were easily washable.
- Spreadability of F2 & F3 was found to be greater than that of the F1.
- F2 & F3 showed better stability even after three months, while in F1, a slight change in homogeneity was observed when kept at 30-40°C.
- No microbial growth was observed in any of the formulation.

We found that both the formulations F2 and F3 can be used further for advanced studies.

S.No	Parameters	Formulation 1 (F1)	Formulation 2 (F2)	Formulation 2 (F3)
1	Color	Pale Yellow	Yellowish green	Brownish yellow
2	Texture	Mucilagenous	Shiny mucilagenous	Smooth shiny gel
3	Odour	Characteristic	Characteristic	Characteristic
4	pH	7-8	7-8	7-8
5	Spreadability	Spreadable	Spreadable	Spreadable
6	Washability	Washable	Washable	Washable
7	Homogeneity	Homogeneous	Homogeneous	Homogeneous
8	Irritancy	No side effect noticed	No side effect noticed	No side effect noticed
9	Stability (after 1-3 months)	No color change No odour change	No color change No odour change Found stable	No color change No odour change Found stable

Table 2: Result of evaluation parameters

Figure 5. pH of the formulation & spreadability

IV. CONCLUSION

Herbal products are in much demand as they have fewer side effects than that of the synthetic ones. The herbal foot care gel prepared using the flax seed oil, flax seed mucilage, aloe gel and glycerine showed satisfactory results in terms of all evaluation parameters carried out for it; and it seems to provide soothing healing properties for cracked heels.

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